

lesser extent, KDML 105 were efficient in internal transport and use of Zn; IR9764, Mahsuri, Kuantik Putih, and to a lesser extent, KDML 105 were efficient in Zn acquisition from the soil. Lines IR8192, FR13A, and Madhukar were responsive to Zn addition as well as efficient in internal use. ■

Genetic variability and path analysis in rice grown in saline soil

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Our study aimed to examine genetic variability, heritability, and correlation coefficients among different characters when rice varieties were grown under saline conditions. We estimated the genetic parameters of seven quantitative characters in 20 rice genotypes grown under saline conditions. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design and replicated three times during 1995-96 on saline soils (4-5 dS m⁻¹) at the Rice Research Station "Jucarito," Granma Province, Cuba. Hills were spaced 20 × 10 cm, with a single seedling hill⁻¹. Observations were recorded on five randomly selected plants replication⁻¹. The mean, standard deviation, phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV), genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV), broad-sense heritability (h²), and genetic advance as a percentage of mean (GA%) were calculated for seven traits. Path coefficient analysis was used to partition the genotypic correlation coefficient into direct and indirect effects.

Significant differences were observed for all traits, indicating great variability between genotypes. PCV was usually higher than GCV, but the difference was very low, indicating less environmental influence on the expression of different traits. The

higher GCV and PCV for grain yield plant⁻¹, panicle weight, and plant height provided better scope for improvement through selection for saline conditions (Table 1).

A moderate amount of variability (11-12%) was observed for panicles plant⁻¹ and filled grains panicle⁻¹, whereas a low GCV and low GA% were observed for panicle length and 1,000-grain weight. These indicated that the characters were under high environmental influence, and that selection based on these characters would be ineffective under saline conditions.

The high value of GCV, h², and GA% estimated for grain yield plant⁻¹, plant height, and panicle weight indicated the predominance of additive gene action, and that direct phenotypic selection based on these traits would be effective for varietal improvement on saline soils.

Grain yield plant⁻¹ was positively and significantly correlated with panicle weight, filled grains panicle⁻¹, 1,000-grain weight, and plant height, but negatively and significantly correlated with panicles plant⁻¹. Panicle length did not show any correlation with yield (Table 2).

The path coefficient analyses also indicated that panicle weight, filled grains panicle⁻¹, and plant height had the largest direct effect on yield. Thus, these three characters emerged as the main components of rice grain yield under saline conditions. Other characters, such as panicles plant⁻¹, panicle length, and 1,000-grain weight, did not show any direct effect on yield, but they influenced yield via plant height. Panicle weight, filled grains panicle⁻¹, and plant height appeared to be the most reliable indices for selection under Cuba's saline conditions. ■

Table 1. Genetic parameters for seven traits in rice varieties grown in saline soil.

Trait	Mean	Standard deviation	PCV ^a	GCV	h ²	GA%
Plant height (cm)	100.5	1.82	28.18	28.16	90.6	30.2
Panicles plant ⁻¹ (no.)	9.6	0.80	11.52	11.48	94.8	21.4
Panicle length (cm)	24.8	2.24	3.00	2.97	37.2	12.9
Panicle weight (g)	4.3	0.52	22.84	22.80	89.4	22.8
Filled grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	92.8	9.60	12.65	12.63	42.5	22.6
1,000-grain weight (g)	29.3	0.80	6.05	6.02	97.0	10.6
Grain yield plant ⁻¹ (g)	12.6	2.62	39.86	39.84	97.2	34.5

^aPCV = phenotypic coefficient of variation, GCV = genotypic coefficient of variation, h² = heritability, GA% = genetic advance as % of mean.

Table 2. Path analysis showing direct and indirect effects on yield.^a

Variable	Plant height	Panicles plant ⁻¹	Panicle length	Panicle weight	Filled grains panicle ⁻¹	1,000-grain weight	Total genotypic correlation with yield
1	0.437	0.145	-0.043	0.078	0.027	-0.088	0.557**
2	-0.148	-0.026	0.040	-0.069	-0.011	0.066	-0.549**
3	0.118	0.107	-0.161	0.055	0.033	-0.082	0.270
4	0.249	0.213	-0.065	1.138	0.017	-0.062	0.691**
5	0.160	0.066	-0.073	0.033	0.575	-0.046	0.875***
6	0.170	0.124	-0.059	0.038	0.015	0.226	0.564**

^aResidual effect = 0.082 direct effects. All others are indirect effects. ** = significant at 5% level, *** = significant at 1% level.